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IMPLEMENTATION OF TRANSCULTURAL NURSING THROUGH DALIHAN NA TOLU COUNSELING IN AN EFFORT TO IMPROVE BLOOD GLUCOSE CONTROL AND QUALITY OF LIFE IN PREDIABETES PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Prediabetes is a condition where blood glucose concentration is higher than normal, but lower than the diabetes threshold, and is a high-risk condition for the development of diabetes. Quality of life is an important aspect in the management of prediabetes; this is related to how sufferers are able to control their blood glucose levels. Efforts that can be made are to improve self-care behavior in prediabetes sufferers, one of which is through dalihan na tolu counseling. The purpose of this study is to analyze efforts to improve blood glucose control and quality of life in prediabetes sufferers using dalihan na tolu counseling based on transcultural nursing. This study is a quantitative study with a quasi-experimental design with a Nonequivalent Control Group with a sample size of 66 consisting of a control group and an intervention group. Data collection was carried out using random blood glucose level examination (KGDS) and Diabetic Quality of Life (DQoL)

questionnaire. The intervention carried out on the respondents in the intervention group was in the form of counseling and assistance by the family (the Dalihan Na Tolu party) for 3 months. Data analysis was carried out using a paired t-test to compare the values before and after the Dalihan Na Tolu counseling activity in the intervention control group. Then an independent t-test compared the control group with the intervention group. After conducting a paired t-test on the control and intervention groups before and after Dalihan Na Tolu counseling, a p-value of 0.000 was obtained. In the independent t-test for the control and intervention groups, a p-value of 0.000 was obtained. This shows that Dalihan Na Tolu counseling is effective in improving blood glucose control and quality of life in prediabetes sufferers. Dalihan Na Tolu counseling is effective as an effort to improve blood glucose control and quality of life in prediabetes sufferers. This is a concrete form of transcultural nursing theory that involves cultural and kinship elements in the process of caring for family members with prediabetes.

KEYWORDS: Blood Glucose Level Control, Quality of life of prediabetes, Dalihan Natolu Counseling, Transcultural Nursing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes is the most common type of diabetes, accounting for more than 90% of all diabetes cases worldwide. Type 2 diabetes is currently the 8th leading cause of disease burden globally and is projected to become the second leading cause by 2050 (1). The cause of type 2 diabetes is not fully understood, but there is a strong association with excess weight, advanced age, ethnicity, and a family history of diabetes. Factors contributing to the risk of type 2 diabetes are thought to include a multi-gene predisposition and environmental triggers (2,3).

Prediabetes (intermediate hyperglycemia) is a high-risk condition for diabetes defined by glycemic variables that are higher than normal, but lower than the diabetes threshold. Approximately 5–10% of people per year with prediabetes will progress to diabetes, with a similar proportion returning to normoglycemia (4) (5). Prediabetes is a serious health condition in which blood sugar levels are higher than normal, but not yet high enough to be diagnosed as type 2 diabetes (5–7).

Prediabetes, typically defined as a blood glucose concentration higher than normal but lower than the diabetes threshold, is a high-risk state for the development of diabetes. The diagnostic criteria for prediabetes have changed over time and vary depending on the institution of origin (7). Prediabetes broadly refers to the intermediate stage between truly normal glucose levels and the clinical entity of type 2 diabetes, which includes IFG and impaired glucose tolerance. IGT and IFG are associated with an increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes in the future (1,8).

Early detection of diabetes and initiation of treatment are crucial for diabetes management and prevention of complications. The longer a person has undiagnosed diabetes, the greater the risk of complications. A person is defined as having undiagnosed diabetes when their blood glucose levels meet diagnostic criteria for diabetes, but the diagnosis has not been confirmed by a healthcare professional (9–11).

By 2024, an estimated 634.8 million adults, or 12% of adults worldwide, will have impaired glucose tolerance (IGT). By 2050, this figure is projected to increase to 846.5 million adults, or 12.9% of all adults. By 2024, an estimated 487.7 million adults, or 9.2% of the global adult population, will have impaired fasting glucose (IFG). An estimated 647.5 million adults or 9.8% of the global adult population are projected to have IFG by 2050. (1).

Quality of life (*QoL*) is an important aspect in

managing prediabetes, because it is not only physiological conditions that need to be considered, but also how sufferers are able to live their daily lives well despite facing the risk of chronic disease. People with prediabetes often experience physical changes such as fatigue, excess weight, or sleep disturbances, which can affect daily activities and fitness. On the other hand, psychological burdens also arise in the form of anxiety, stress, and worry about the possibility of developing diabetes, which impact emotional well-being and motivation to carry out self-care (12).

Efforts to improve prediabetes self-care include education. Education is conducted to enhance efforts to promote healthy living in the prevention and management of DM holistically. DM education is education and training regarding knowledge and skills for DM patients to support behavioral changes, increase patient understanding of their disease, thereby achieving optimal health, psychological adjustments, and improving quality of life (13). The approach used in health education interventions is counseling. Education based on the theory of planned behavior, by holding face-to-face meetings and following up on samples after the educational intervention, can promote a healthy lifestyle for prediabetic women. Therefore, designing and implementing similar interventions in all prediabetic individuals seems necessary. (14). Other studies also show that creating awareness of diabetes risk in at-risk groups and increasing counseling of at-risk groups by doctors/healthcare providers can be key to preventing diabetes. (15).

One of the nursing theories that can be applied in efforts to improve self-care and the quality of life of prediabetes sufferers is the Transcultural Nursing theory developed by Madeleine Leininger (16).

From a social and cultural perspective, the quality of life of people with prediabetes is often influenced by their family environment and cultural values. For example, in societies that value togetherness during meals or traditional celebrations, people with prediabetes often struggle to control their eating habits. A lack of family understanding of the importance of a healthy lifestyle can reduce social support, which should be a protective factor in managing prediabetes (17,18).

There are several factors related to a person's behavior. Cultural and social structure factors included in this theory include technology, religion, family and kinship, politics, cultural beliefs and practices, economics, physical conditions, and biological factors that influence care and influence health/well-being patterns and well-being (19,20).

A reduced quality of life can lead to poor adherence to self-care behaviors such as diet, physical activity, regular health check-ups, and stress management. However, a good quality of life has been shown to be positively associated with blood glucose control, improved mental health, and the prevention of metabolic complications. Therefore, addressing the quality of life of prediabetes sufferers is an integral part of efforts to prevent the disease from progressing to diabetes mellitus (4,21).

Viewed from the aspect of kinship and cultural practices, the city of Padangsidempuan has elements of Dalihan Natolu culture that are very closely related to the practice of daily life. *Dalihan Na Tolu* culture not only regulates relationships between individuals, but also influences people's thought patterns and behavior in daily life, including in terms of decision making, diet, health care, and attitudes towards illness. In the context of health, this culture can act as a source of social and emotional support, because the extended family and relatives have a moral responsibility to help family members who are sick (22) (23). *Dalihan Natolu* becomes a framework that includes blood relatives and marriage relationships that connect one group (24,25).

2. METHODS

This study is a quantitative study with a quasi-experimental design with a Nonequivalent Control Group consisting of a control group and an intervention group (26,27). The population in this study were prediabetes sufferers in Padangsidempuan City. The sample in this study

consisted of 33 respondents as the control group, and 33 respondents as the intervention group selected using a *purposive sampling technique*. Data collection was carried out using several questionnaires, including a questionnaire on respondent characteristics consisting of age, gender, education, occupation, and socioeconomic status. Then for the research variables, a random blood glucose level examination (KGDS) and a *Diabetic Quality of Life* (DQoL) questionnaire were carried out using the Recall method for the previous 7 days (28,29). The intervention carried out on respondents in the intervention group was in the form of counseling and mentoring by Dalihan Natolu for 3 months which aimed to improve blood glucose control and the quality of life of prediabetes sufferers. Counseling for prediabetes patients and the application of transcultural nursing from the aspect of kinship and culture in the southern Tapanuli region can be combined with the Dalihan Natolu Elements consisting of Mora, kahanggi and Anak Boru. In this study it is called "Dalihan Natolu Counseling". Data analysis was carried out using a paired t-test to compare the values before and after the Dalihan Na Tolu counseling activity in the intervention control group. Then the independent t-test compared the control group with the intervention group (30).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Respondent Characteristics

The following are the characteristics of respondents based on gender, education, Job/Profession, socioeconomic status, and age.

Table 1: Respondent Characteristics Based on Gender, Education, Occupation, Socioeconomic Status, And Age (N = 66).

Characteristics	Control Group		Intervention Group	
	f	%	f	%
Gender				
Man	13	39.3	13	39.3
Woman	20	61.7	20	61.7
Education				
Elementary School	4	12.1	3	9.1
Senior High School	21	63.7	25	75.8
College	8	24.2	5	15.1
Job/Profession				
Housewife	9	27.3	4	12.1
Farmer	9	27.3	8	24.2
Private sector employee	7	21.2	7	21.2
Trader	5	15.1	9	27.3
Civil Servants/Police/State-Owned Enterprises	3	9.1	5	15.1
Socioeconomic Status				
Low	19	57.6	15	45.4
Intermediate	7	21.2	15	45.4
High	7	21.2	3	9.1
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD

Age	47.36	8.24	47.33	7.51
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Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents in both the control and intervention groups were female, with 20 respondents (61.7%) in both groups. The majority of respondents had high school education in the control group (21 respondents (63.7%) and in the intervention group (25 respondents (76.8%). For occupation, in the control group, the majority of respondents were housewives (9 respondents (27.3%) and farmers (9 respondents (27.3%), while in the intervention group, the majority of respondents were traders (9 respondents (27.3%). The majority of respondents had low socioeconomic status in the control group (19 respondents (57.6%),

while in the intervention group, the majority were low (15 respondents (45.4%) and middle (15 respondents (45.4%). The average age in both the control and intervention groups was 47.3 years.

3.2. Blood Glucose Level Control and Quality of Life in Prediabetes

The following are random blood glucose levels and quality of life in prediabetes sufferers in the control group and intervention group before and after intervention in the form of dalihan na tolu counseling and assistance from dalihan na tolu.

Table 2: Random Blood Glucose Levels and Quality of Life in Prediabetes Patients in the Control Group and Intervention Group Before and After Intervention in the Form of Dalihan Na Tolu Counseling and Assistance from Dalihan Na Tolu (N = 66).

Variable	Mean	Δx	SD	Min	Max	P value
Blood glucose levels during prediabetes						
Control group						
Pre	180.91	3.32	10.16	156	198.00	0,000
Post	177.68		9.66	155	192.00	
Intervention group						
Pre	176.94	12.76	11.92	157	197.00	0,000
Post	164.18		10.85	146	181.00	
Quality of Life for Prediabetes						
Control group						
Pre	43.87	2.88	8.23	30.00	58.00	0,000
Post	46.75		7.95	30.00	59.00	
Intervention group						
Pre	43.21	7.54	6.93	28.00	58.00	0,000
Post	50.75		6.60	36.00	60.00	

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 2 shows that the results of random blood glucose level examinations carried out by respondents in the control group before the intervention had an average score of 180.90 gr/dL and after 3 months of random blood glucose level examinations, the average blood glucose level was 177.68 gr/dL. There was a decrease in blood glucose levels of around 3.32 gr/dL and when the paired t test was carried out in the control group, the p value was 0.000, which means there was a change in blood glucose levels in the control group.

The same thing was found in the intervention group; there was a decrease in blood glucose levels before and after the dalihan na tolu counseling intervention. At the beginning, the results of the random blood glucose level examination were 176.94 gr / dL, but there was a decrease in the value of the random blood glucose level by 12.76 gr / dL so that in the measurement after 3 months of the dalihan na tolu counseling intervention, the results of the

random blood glucose level examination were again obtained with an average blood glucose level of 164.18 gr / dL. And when the paired t test was conducted in the intervention group, a p value of 0.000 was obtained, which showed that dalihan na tolu counseling was effective in efforts to improve blood glucose control in prediabetic patients.

The quality-of-life score for prediabetes patients was 43.87, and after three months of re-measurement, the score was 46.75. There was a 2.88 increase in the quality-of-life score. A paired t-test for the control group yielded a p-value of 0.000, indicating an improvement in the quality of life in the control group compared to prediabetes.

The same thing was found in the intervention group; there was an increase in the quality-of-life score before and after the dalihan na tolu counseling intervention. At the beginning, the quality-of-life score was 43.21, but there was an increase in the quality-of-life score of 7.54 so that in the

measurement after 3 months of the dalihan na tolu counseling intervention, the quality-of-life score of prediabetes sufferers was 50.75. And when the *paired t test was conducted* in the intervention group, a *p value* of 0.000 was obtained, indicating that dalihan na tolu counseling was effective in improving the quality of life in prediabetes sufferers.

3.3. Effectiveness Of Dalihan Na Tolu

Table 3: Results Of the Independent T-Test on Blood Glucose Level Control and Quality of Life of Prediabetes Sufferers in the Control Group and Intervention Group After Intervention in the Form of Dalihan Na Tolu Counseling and Mentoring from Dalihan Na Tolu (N = 66).

Variable	Mean	Δx	SD	Min	Max	P value
Post-Intervention Blood Glucose Level Control						
Control group	177.68	13.50	9.66	155	192.00	0,000
Intervention group	164.18		10.85	146	181.00	
Post-Intervention Quality of Life						
Control group	46.75	4.00	16.24	34.00	80.00	0,000
Intervention group	50.75		17.64	44.00	110.00	

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 3 shows that there was a difference in the average blood glucose levels in the control and intervention groups after the intervention in the form of dalihan na tolu counseling. In the control group, the blood glucose level after 3 months was 177.68 gr/dL, and in the intervention group, the blood glucose level was 164.18 gr/dL, there was a difference in the average blood glucose level of 13.50 gr/dL between the control and intervention groups. And when the independent t-test was conducted in the control and intervention groups, a *p value* of 0.000 was obtained, which indicates that Dalihan Natolu counseling is effective in increasing blood glucose control in prediabetes sufferers.

The same thing was also found in the quality of life of prediabetes patients; there was a difference in the average quality of life scores in the control and intervention groups after the intervention in the form of dalihan na tolu counseling. In the control group, the quality-of-life score after 3 months was 46.75, and in the intervention group, the quality-of-life score was 50.75, there was a difference in the average quality of life score of 4.00 between the control and intervention groups. And when the independent t-test was conducted In the control and intervention groups, a *p value* of 0.000 was obtained, which indicates that Dalihan Natolu counseling is effective in improving the quality of life in prediabetes sufferers.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Respondent Characteristics

Counseling on Blood Glucose Level Control and Quality of Life in Prediabetes Patients

The following are the results of the independent t-test on the control of blood glucose levels and the quality of life of prediabetes sufferers in the control group and the intervention group after the intervention in the form of Dalihan Na Tolu counseling and mentoring from Dalihan Na Tolu.

The research results showed that the characteristics of respondents varied from gender, education, occupation, socioeconomic status, and age. Several studies also stated that the characteristics of diabetes sufferers are mostly women, and with education around junior high school to high school, and age under 60 years and low to middle socioeconomic status (31). However, in practice, female diabetes sufferers are also better able to maintain their quality of life compared to male sufferers (32). Other studies show that women are significantly associated with the occurrence of prediabetes. Women are at 0.4 times higher risk of developing prediabetes (33). Women of childbearing age are less susceptible to cardiovascular disease due to the protective effect of estrogen. Estrogen generally lowers circulating triglyceride and LDL-C levels, while increasing HDL-C levels. However, several studies mention the development of cardiovascular disease in women with lower blood glucose levels than men (3) (34).

Gender significantly contributes to diabetes *self-care*. It has been shown that female clients demonstrate better diabetes *self-care behaviors* than male clients. Both male and female diabetes clients should engage in diabetes *self-care activities*, but women appear to be more concerned about their health, making optimal efforts to self-treat their illness (35).

The research results showed that the majority of respondents were of low and middle socioeconomic status. Socioeconomic status influences diabetes *self-care*. A positive relationship can be observed, where

clients with a high socioeconomic status will improve their diabetes *self-care behavior*. Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease that requires quite expensive treatment. If a client's economic status is inadequate, it will make it difficult for them to visit health care centers regularly, making it difficult to monitor the client's health status and making them more likely to experience diabetes complications (36) .

Education and occupation also influence blood glucose control and quality of life. Some people with prediabetes are not well aware of their health status, so they delay activities that could improve their quality of life (34) .

4.2. Blood Glucose Control and Quality of Life in Prediabetes

Prediabetes represents a window of opportunity during which modifiable risk factors, such as overweight/obesity, a high-energy diet, and physical inactivity, can be targeted to prevent or delay the development of type 2 diabetes (2) . Lifestyle interventions in individuals with prediabetes may also have beneficial effects on the development of cardiovascular disease, microvascular complications, and cardiovascular and all-cause mortality in the long term. Lifestyle interventions in individuals with impaired glucose tolerance delay the onset of type 2 diabetes and reduce the incidence of cardiovascular events, microvascular complications, cardiovascular and all-cause mortality, and increase life expectancy. These findings provide strong justification for continuing to implement and expand the use of such interventions to curb the global epidemic of type 2 diabetes and its consequences (2,37) .

Blood glucose control is a crucial component of improving self-care and the quality of life for people with prediabetes. This will demonstrate whether the education provided by healthcare workers and others is being implemented by those with prediabetes (38) .

self-care is a program or action that must be carried out throughout the client's life and is the full responsibility of each diabetes client. Activities included in diabetes *self-care* include regulating diet, physical exercise , blood sugar monitoring, medication, and foot care (39) .

Blood glucose control in individuals with prediabetes should focus on returning to normoglycemia rather than simply maintaining prediabetes. A previous study in the Middle East found that diabetes progression was significantly lower in individuals who returned to normoglycemia than in those who consistently maintained prediabetes. This was due to improvements in

insulin sensitivity and pancreatic β -cell function during the intervention. The study also showed that the proportion of individuals who became normoglycemic was significantly higher in the intervention group than in the control group. Assuming this reversal is temporary, the risk of prediabetes individuals progressing to type 2 diabetes mellitus is certainly reduced (40) .

Prediabetes care cannot be done by the sufferer alone, but also requires help and support from others. As found by previous research, people with prediabetes often need encouragement to discuss the responsibilities, choices, and behaviors they follow to support self-care to improve their health and well-being (41) .

The study results showed that the overall quality of life of individuals with prediabetes did not differ significantly from that of subjects with normal glucose tolerance, whereas for participants with diabetes, the quality was lower (mainly due to the presence of vascular complications). However, some components of quality of life were already affected in prediabetic IGT, particularly mobility and psychological distress. Understanding the stage of diabetes at which health status declines will allow for prioritization of intervention efforts and more effective targeting of policies and strategic interventions to improve health outcomes. Therefore, quality of life issues (particularly physical and psycho-emotional issues) should be investigated when individuals with prediabetes are diagnosed in routine clinical practice, as their identification could potentially lead to more effective overall management of their condition (42) .

4.3. Effectiveness Of Dalihan Natolu Counseling on Blood Glucose Level Control and Quality of Life in Prediabetes Patients

People with prediabetes are at high risk of developing other complications, such as the development of diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular problems, and so on. Prediabetes is positively correlated with the risk of all-cause mortality and the incidence of cardiovascular outcomes, coronary heart disease, stroke, chronic kidney disease, cancer, and dementia (43) . Psychologically, high levels of distress are also found in people with diabetes. Therefore, special attention is needed by patients, their families, and the medical team to incorporate distress evaluation as part of routine procedures in diabetes care, and recommend that doctors implement a comprehensive approach in diabetes management, which is very important (31) .

The quality of life of people with prediabetes is

also influenced by their daily activities. Studies have shown that people with prediabetes who achieve prediabetes physical activity guidelines have higher levels of physical and mental quality of life than those who are inactive. Furthermore, these results support the rationale for developing strategically designed physical activity programs for individuals with prediabetes (44).

A reduced quality of life can lead to poor adherence to self-care behaviors such as diet, physical activity, regular health check-ups, and stress management. However, a good quality of life has been shown to be positively associated with blood glucose control, improved mental health, and the prevention of metabolic complications. Therefore, addressing the quality of life of prediabetes sufferers is an integral part of efforts to prevent the disease from progressing to diabetes mellitus (4,21).

On research conducted in India also shows that there has been a decline

A statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$, with 95% CI) difference was found in blood sugar levels from baseline to post-counseling, as evidenced by a decrease in complaints of diabetes symptoms (45). Other studies also show that counseling provides respondents with an understanding of their illness, which then encourages them to manage their illness and subsequently plan what actions to take to manage their illness. Ultimately, this home care counseling enables respondents to accept their illness and be wiser in living with their illness, thereby improving their quality of life and preventing complications (46).

One approach that can be taken is the Transcultural Nursing approach, which involves several factors in an effort to improve self-care behavior in prediabetes sufferers. Cultural and social structural factors included in this theory include technology, religion, family and kinship, politics, cultural beliefs and practices, economics, physical conditions, and biological factors that influence care and influence health/well-being patterns and well-being (29,39).

Various sociocultural factors influence public health, including kinship and cultural practices. These two factors can be modified through the development of counseling methods appropriate to the local cultural context. Counseling itself is a personal relationship between two individuals: a counselor with specialized skills and a client as the recipient of assistance. In this face-to-face interaction, the counselor plays a role in creating a learning environment that enables the client to understand themselves, their current situation, and the

possibilities they can shape for the future by utilizing their potential. The ultimate goal is to improve the well-being of individuals and society, while equipping clients with problem-solving skills and identifying future needs. (47).

In the context of the South Tapanuli community, the counseling approach for prediabetes sufferers can be linked to Transcultural Nursing through the integration of Dalihan Na Tolu values. The Dalihan Na Tolu system consists of three essential elements – Mora, Kahanggi, and Anak Boru – which are interconnected and inseparable. This term originates from the metaphor of a three-legged stove, which symbolizes social balance in the Batak Angkola community. Each element has its own social responsibility and role in maintaining harmonious kinship relationships. (48,49). Therefore, in this research, this approach is called Dalihan Na Tolu Counseling.

The results of the study indicate that the implementation of Dalihan Na Tolu Counseling is effective in helping control blood glucose levels and improving the quality of life of prediabetic patients. In line with these findings, other studies confirm that the success of preventing Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus is highly dependent on family involvement, because the family is an important part of the Dalihan Na Tolu social and cultural system. The role of kinship includes the habit of helping each other, sharing roles, providing advice, and maintaining social relationships through various forms of support, both moral and material. Values such as visiting relatives, giving gifts, and mutual cooperation in social responsibility remain part of the culture of the South Tapanuli community even though there have been several shifts (50,51). The Dalihan Na Tolu kinship system is still held by the South Tapanuli community, even though there have been shifts (40).

Counseling for prediabetes sufferers generally focuses on lifestyle changes, so the involvement of family members and relatives is essential. In this study, the counseling process was conducted in conjunction with support from Dalihan Na Tolu, who are the respondents' closest relatives. Other studies also indicate that behavioral change takes time, so ongoing support from Mora, Kahanggi, Anak Boru, and local traditional and community leaders is needed to strengthen the effectiveness of lifestyle counseling (52).

In addition, previous studies have shown that individuals who attend counseling sessions tend to have a higher awareness of the risks and complications of diabetes compared to those who do not (53). For example, in Finland, a lifestyle

counseling model has become part of general nursing practice. In this system, nurses play an active role in helping patients make changes to their health behaviors by utilizing various supporting theories and models. One key to its success is collaboration between nurses and patients in setting shared goals, an approach that is now a priority in the country's type 2 diabetes prevention program. (54) .

Meanwhile, the main obstacles in prediabetes care are often caused by low patient compliance with self-management and a lack of awareness of the importance of maintaining health. According to Leininger, research and the implementation of evidence-based nursing practices that are sensitive to culture are needed. She emphasized the importance of nursing education that prepares nurses with cross-cultural competence to be able to bridge the paradigm shift from traditional practices to modern approaches in health care, especially in cases of prediabetes (39) .

5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1. Conclusion

Understanding the culture of the

Padangsidimpuan community is crucial for integrating a transcultural approach into public health programs. This approach allows for more acceptable, effective, and sustainable health interventions, as they are tailored to local values and perspectives. Dalihan Natolu counseling is effective in improving blood glucose control and the quality of life for people with prediabetes. This is a concrete example of *transcultural nursing theory* , which incorporates cultural and kinship elements into the care process for family members with prediabetes.

5.2. Suggestion

The Padangsidimpuan City Government, particularly the Health Department, is expected to increase efforts to encourage healthy lifestyle changes in the community, particularly in preventing non-communicable diseases and their complications. Furthermore, it is recommended that promotional and preventive programs integrate more deeply with local cultural values, particularly elements of Dalihan Na Tolu, to make the approach more relevant and acceptable to the community.

Ethical Clearance: This research has undergone ethical review by the research ethics committee of the Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, with registration number 1796/UN4.14.1/TP.01.02/2024.

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